

TOXICITY EVALUATION OF *CEIBA PENTANDRA* (L) GAERTN ACETONE LEAF
EXTRACT USING *DROSOPHILA MELANOGASTER* MODELJoy J. Adeyemi^{*1,2}, John O. Ayorinde¹, Amos O. Abolaji²¹Department of Pharmaceutics, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.²Drosophila Research Laboratory, Department of Biochemistry, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.***Corresponding Author: Joy J. Adeyemi**

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ABSTRACT

Toxicity studies are used to determine the safety of materials with pharmacological actions when used in animal models. It also establishes the safe limits in conditions of use. There have been previous reports as regards the safety of *Ceiba pentandra* (*C. pentandra*) extracts in mammalian models which have been reported to be up to 5000 mg/ 5g diet, however, its acetone extract has never been reported. Further, the use of *Drosophila melanogaster* models has not been used to determine the plant's safety limits. This study, therefore, is aimed at evaluating the acute toxicity of the acetone extract of *C. pentandra* leaves, using *Drosophila melanogaster* models. Mucilage was obtained by soaking the dried leaves in acetone for two days. The phytochemical screening of the extract was carried out. The acetone extract was administered to *Drosophila melanogaster* in various doses (1mg, 1.5mg, 2mg and 2.5 mg)/ 5g diet and at higher concentrations. There was improvement of survival of *Drosophila melanogaster* at low concentrations of the extracts whereas at higher concentrations exceeding 75mg/ 5g diet their survival rate reduced. It can be concluded from this study that it is relatively safe at lower dietary levels while exhibiting a dose-dependent toxicity.

KEYWORDS: Toxicity studies; Pharmacological actions; *Ceiba pentandra*; *Drosophila melanogaster*; mucilage.**INTRODUCTION**

Toxicity studies can be defined as a set of systematic investigations used to assess the harmful effects of drugs and chemicals on living organisms, especially animals. It is crucial in drug development and ensures that potential medicinal products do not pose significant risks to human health. These tests can be categorized based on duration and dosing frequency, into acute, sub-acute, sub-chronic, and chronic toxicity studies.

- Acute Toxicity Studies assess the immediate effects of a single dose, often measured by the median lethal dose (LD₅₀)^[1]
- Sub-acute and Sub-chronic Studies evaluate long-term effects focusing on repeated dosing and its impact on various biological systems.^[2]
- Chronic Toxicity Studies investigate prolonged exposure effects, typically lasting a significant portion of the animal's lifespan.^[3]

Toxicity studies are very important in drug development being integral to preclinical safety assessments. It helps to prevent the clinical use of harmful substances and identify adverse effects while also guiding the safe dosage for human trials.^[4] Findings obtained from these studies inform regulatory decisions and contribute to the safety profile of new compounds.^[1]

Animals became standardized for toxicity testing in the early 20th century and have been used since.^[5] However, contemporary practices are increasingly scrutinized, which has resulted in the development of ethical frameworks aimed at reducing animal use in research. Therefore, there is a growing shift towards alternative methods in order to reduce reliance on animal testing.^[6]

Drosophila melanogaster, commonly known as the fruit fly, is used in this research because it is a widely used

model organism in biological and medical research because of its numerous advantages over traditional animal models like mice and rats. The advantages of using *Drosophila* over other animal models are manifold because it shares a significant portion of its genetic makeup with humans, with about 60% of human disease-causing genes having recognizable counterparts in the fruit fly allowing researchers to study human diseases effectively.^[7] Secondly, is its cost-effectiveness and ease of maintenance and also its short life cycle and high reproductive rate which enable rapid generation turnover, facilitating quick experimental results.^[8,9]

C. pentandra (L.) Gaertn (family Malvaceae) is a plant that has a wide distribution in equatorial Africa and naturalized humid areas^[10] and commonly known as silk tree or kapok tree.^[11]

Its different parts have been used for medicinal and non-medicinal purposes. In Southeast Asian countries, its leaves have been used to treat fever, cough, hoarseness, and venereal diseases. The bark has been employed in treating fever, asthma, gonorrhoea, and diarrhoea, and as an aphrodisiac, while the root has been used as a diuretic and febrifuge.^[11,12,13]

C. pentandra plant contains a number of secondary metabolites which are assumed to be responsible for its promising medicinal properties like antioxidative^[14], hypoglycaemic^[15], anti-bacterial^[16] anti-convulsant and antitumor activity.^[17] Also in drug formulation, it is useful as a suitable excipient.^[18]

Various studies have been done to determine both acute and subacute toxicity assessments of this plant using its various extracts in animal models. The findings consistently showed a low toxicity profile, with LD₅₀ as high as 5000mg/ kg in rats suggesting that *C. pentandra* is relatively safe for consumption.^[19] However its toxicity studies have never been carried out using alternative models like *Drosophila melanogaster*.

Therefore, this study aims to study the toxicity of *C. pentandra* acetone extract using *Drosophila melanogaster* model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Plant material: *C. pentandra* leaves were collected from Omu-aran in Kwara state. It was authenticated at the University of Ibadan Herbarium and given voucher number **UIH-22406**.

Chemicals and reagents: The chemicals, solvents and reagents used were of analytical grade (Sigma Aldrick, UK).

METHODS

Extraction of *C. pentandra* leaves

The leaves were air-dried, and extracted using the cold maceration method. The plant material was treated with petroleum ether to remove pigments and fats; soaked in water for 5 hours, boiled for 30 minutes and allowed to stand for 30 minutes so that the mucilage can be leaked into the water. The material was squeezed from the 8 folds of muslin cloth to remove the marc. Equal volume of acetone was added to the filtrate to remove the mucilage. The mucilage was separated, dried in the oven at 45°C, sieved twice and stored in a dessicator.

Qualitative analysis of phytochemical constituents

Phytochemical screening of the different extracts were carried out using the standard procedures as described by^[20]

Culture of *Drosophila melanogaster*: *Drosophila melanogaster* (Harwich strain), primarily sourced from the National Species Stock Center (Bowling Green, OH, USA) were cultured and maintained in the *Drosophila* Laboratory, Biochemistry Department, University of Ibadan, Nigeria as described by.^[21]

Survival study: To determine the concentration and duration of exposure to *C. pentandra* leaf extract. The flies (both genders, 1-3 days old) were exposed to different concentrations (1 mg, 1.5 mg, 2 mg, 2.5 mg) respectively per 5 g diet over 14 days with daily mortality rate recorded and percentage survival determined.

The test was repeated using 37.5mg, 75 mg and 150 mg per 5 g diet respectively.

Five groups of *Drosophila melanogaster* were used in subacute toxicity study of acetone extract of the leaves of *C. pentandra* and each group consists of 30 flies. The groups and treatment were designed as follows:

- Group 1 - Control treated with water (0.2 µl)
- Group 2 - *C. pentandra* (1 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)
- Group 3 - *C. pentandra* (1.5 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)
- Group 4 - *C. pentandra* (2 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)
- Group 5 - *C. pentandra* (2.5 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)

- Group 1 - Control treated with water (0.2 µl)
- Group 2 - *C. pentandra* (37.5 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)
- Group 3 - *C. pentandra* (75 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)
- Group 4 - *C. pentandra* (150 mg/ 5 g diet, p.o.)

Statistical analysis: Statistical difference was determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and p<0.05 was adjudged significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Qualitative analysis of *C. pentandra* leaf acetone extract.

Phytochemical Constituents	Results
Saponins	++
Tannins	+
Flavonoids	+
Cardiac glycosides	-
Steroids	++
Terpenoids	+
Phenols	+
Anthraquinones	+
Alkaloids	+

Survival Results

Fig. I: Survival of *Ceiba pentandra* leaf acetone extracts at 1, 1.5, 2 and 2.5 mg per 5 g diet.

Fig. II: Survival of *Ceiba pentandra* leaf acetone extracts at 37.50 mg, 75 mg and 150 mg per 5 g diet.

Fig. III: Bar graph comparing the negative geotaxis of the control to *C. pentandra* extract administered at different doses.

DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis

C. pentandra leaves contain various phytochemicals such as flavonoids, saponins, steroids, tannins, triterpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, and resins, which have been confirmed through screening and metabolic profiling.^[22,23]

The antioxidant property of this plant can be linked to the presence of flavonoids, phenols, and tannins which scavenge free radicals and reduce oxidative stress which inhibit inflammatory pathways.^[24] To a certain extent, *C. pentandra* leaf acetone extract exhibits antimicrobial activity similar to literature due to the presence of alkaloids, saponins, and tannins because they have the ability to inhibit the growth of certain bacteria and fungi.^[25] These phytochemicals are responsible for *C. pentandra* potential usefulness in managing oxidative-related diseases, microbial infections and inflammatory conditions.^[26]

Survival of *C. pentandra* leaf acetone extracts

Figures 1 and 2 show the effect of varying concentrations of the acetone leaf extract of *C. pentandra* on the survival of *D. melanogaster* after a 14- day exposure. It was observed that at lower concentrations of <75mg/ 5 g diet, the survival rate was improved compared to that of the control. This survival rate increased with increase in concentrations (from 1mg/ 5 g diet to 70mg/ 5 g diet) of the extract, while showing a declining survival rate at values above 70 mg/ 5 g diet.

Negative geotaxis in *Drosophila melanogaster*, the innate behaviour of climbing against gravity when startled, has significant implications for understanding various biological and pathological processes. This behaviour is a valuable tool for studying locomotor function, aging and neurodegeneration.

Negative geotaxis declines with age in *Drosophila*, mirroring age-related locomotor impairments in humans.

This decline is primarily due to reduced climbing speed, making it a useful model for studying aging and neurodegenerative diseases.^[27]

It can be observed from the result obtained that *C. pentandra* acetone extract did not negatively impair the climbing activity of the flies at reduced doses but at a higher dose there was a slight reduction in this property showing that it is not likely to induce aging and neurodegenerative diseases at lower doses.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that *C. pentandra* acetone extract exhibits a dose-dependent toxicity. Despite this plant has potential for pharmacological, pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications, these findings highlight the importance of dose optimization. Furthermore, the suitability of *D. melanogaster* in assessing the toxicity of plant extracts was established.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Saganuwan A. Toxicity studies of drugs and chemicals in animals: An overview. *Bulg J Vet Med*, 2017; 20(4): 291–318. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.15547/BJVM.983>
2. Mhaske S, Mhaske S, Pagare A, Harshda N. A review on long term chronic toxicity study. *Int J Pharm Sci Med*, 2023; 1(0). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.47760/ijpsm.2023.v08i10.008>
3. Perrimon N. New advances in *Drosophila* provide opportunities to study gene functions. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.*, 1998; 95(17): 9716-9717.

- Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.95.17.9716>
4. Remya NS, Sangeetha V, Mohanan PV. Toxicity studies of biomedical products. In: Mohanan PV, editor. *Toxicity in Biomedical Products*. Amsterdam: Elsevier; 2022. p. 483–500. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-823966-7.00010-4>
 5. Jacobs AC, Hatfield KP. *History of Chronic Toxicity and Animal Carcinogenicity Studies for Pharmaceuticals*. Vet Pathol. 2013. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0300985812450727>
 6. Sántha M. *Biologia futura: Animal testing in drug development—the past, the present and the future*. Acta Biol Hung. 2020; 71(4): 443–452. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42977-020-00050-4>
 7. Koehler S, Huber TB. Insights into human kidney function from the study of *Drosophila*. *Pediatr Nephrol*. 2023; 1–13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00467-023-05996-w>
 8. Huo G, Lu J, Qu Z, Lin Z, Zhang D, Yang Y, Li B. The applications and advantages of *Drosophila melanogaster* in cancer research. *Hereditas (Beijing)*. 2014; 36(1): 30–40. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3724/SP.J.1005.2014.00030>
 9. Jennings BH. *Drosophila—a versatile model in biology & medicine*. *Materials Today*. 2011; 14(5): 190–195. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021\(11\)70113-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021(11)70113-4)
 10. Pezzini FF, Dexter KG, de Carvalho-Sobrinho JC, Kider CA, Nicholls JA, de Queiroz LP, Pennington RT. Phylogeny and biogeography of *Ceiba Mill* (Malvaceae Bombacoideae). *Front Biogeogr*. 2021; 13(2): 49226.
 11. Sahid M, Zeven AC, editors. *Ceiba pentandra (L.) Gaertn*. In: *Plant Resources of South-East Asia No. 17: Fiber Plants*. PROSEA Foundation; 2003.
 12. Lim TK. *Ceiba pentandra*. In: O’Connell WD, editor. *Edible Medicinal and Non-medicinal Plants*. Vol 3. Dordrecht: Springer; 2012; 540–549. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6195-3_54
 13. Elumalai A, Mathangi N, Didala A, Kasarla R, Venkatesh Y. A review on *Ceiba pentandra* and its medicinal features. *Asian J Pharm Tech*. 2012; 2: 83–86.
 14. Nandeesh R, Srinivasa B, Kumar A, Lakshman K. Evaluation of hair growth activity of *Buxus wallichiana* Baill extracts in rats. *Iran J Basic Med Sci*. 2008; 11(4): 236–241.
 15. Ngounou FN, Meli AL, Lontsi D, Sonndengam BL, Atta-Ur-Rahman, Choudhary MI. New isoflavone from *Ceiba pentandra*. *Phytochemistry*. 2000; 54(1): 107–110.
 16. Bhavani R, Bhuvaneshwari E, Rajeshkumar S. Antibacterial and antioxidant activity of ethanolic extract of *Ceiba pentandra* leaves and its phytochemical analysis using GC-MS. *Res J Pharm Technol*. 2016; 9(11): 1922–1926. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-360X.2016.00393.0>
 17. Orabi MA, Abouelela ME, Darwish FM, Abdelkader MS, Elsadek BE, Al Awadh AA, et al. *Ceiba pentandra* ethyl acetate extract improves doxorubicin antitumor outcomes against chemically induced liver cancer in rat model: A study supported by UHPLC-Q-TOF-MS/MS identification of the bioactive phytochemicals. *Front Pharmacol*. 2024; 15: 1337910. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2024.1337910>
 18. Ayorinde JO, Okonye EO, Adetunji OA, Odeniyi MA. Material and excipient properties of *Ceiba pentandra* mucilage in diclofenac matrix tablets. *Trop J Nat Prod Res.*, 2022; 6(3): 408–415. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5555/20220191073>
 19. Amani Gnamien et al. Acute and subacute toxicities of an aqueous leaves extract of *Ceiba pentandra* (bombacaceae), a antihypertensive plant, and its ethanolic fraction in wistar rats. *J Pharmacogn Phytochem*. 2024; 13(3): 23–30. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.22271/phyto.2024.v13.i3a.14939>
 20. Sofowora A. *Medicinal plants and traditional medicine in Africa*. 3rd ed. Ibadan: Spectrum Books; 2008. (Original work published 1988)
 21. Farombi EO, Abolaji AO, Farombi TH, Oropo AS, Owoje OA, Awunah MT. *Garcinia kola* seed biflavonoid fraction (Kolaviron), increases longevity and attenuates rotenone-induced toxicity in *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*. 2018; 145: 39–45.
 22. Dalhatu AS, Imman ST, Namadina MM, Sani ZM, Muhammad YY. Metabolic profile assessment of phytochemicals in *Ceiba pentandra (L.) Gaertn*, from Zaria City, Nigeria. *FUDMA J Sci.*, 2020; 4(3): 426–436. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2020-0403-410>
 23. Ayorinde JO, Okonye EO. Antioxidant properties and effects of formulation variables on *Ceiba pentandra* microspheres. *Niger J Pharm Res.*, 2023; 19(1): 1–16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5555/20230191016>
 24. Wuyt AK, Nguelefack-Mbuyo EP, Fofie CK, Nguelefack TB. The methanol extract of *Ceiba pentandra* reverses monosodium glutamate-induced cardiometabolic syndrome in rats via the regulation of dyslipidemia, inflammation, oxidative stress, and insulin sensitization. *Heliyon*. 2023; 9(2): e13689. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13689>
 25. Parulekar G. Antibacterial and phytochemical analysis of *Ceiba pentandra (L.)* Seed extracts. *J Pharmacogn Phytochem*. 2017; 6(3): 586–589. Available from: <https://www.phytojournal.com/archives/2017.v6.i3.1276/antibacterial-and-phytochemical-analysis-of-ceiba-pentandra-l-seed-extracts>
 26. Silué GNA, Belemlilga MB, Djadji TLT, Traoré KTL, Boly GAL, Koala M, Kouakou-Siransy G. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities assessment of an aqueous extract of *Ceiba pentandra*

- (L.) Gaertn (Malvaceae). RPS Pharmacology and Reports. 2023; 2(4): rqad037. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.30954/rppr/2023.rqad037>
27. Li QF, et al. Effects of modest hypoxia and exercise on cardiac function, sleep-activity, and negative geotaxis behaviour of aged female *Drosophila*. Front Physiol. 2020; 10: 1610. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2019.01610>